

Situation needs analysis: A framework for developing an ESP course tailored for Iranian bankers and finance professionals

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International banking and its associated enterprises have experienced significant growth in recent times. As a result of this expansion, bank personnel must possess the ability to communicate appropriately, and effective English for Specific Purposes (ESP) programs need to be implemented accordingly. The present study investigated the language needs of bank employees in the International Banking Division (IBD) of Bank Melli Iran (BMI) using Dudley-Evans and St. John's (1998) needs analysis model. The research adopted a quantitative and descriptive methodology (1) to adequately describe the intended population's situation and (2) to design an ESP course for them. Of 130 bankers ($N=130$), finance professionals, and bank managers as the whole population, 90 participants accepted to take the proficiency test, and 88 participants returned the questionnaire. Interviews were conducted with 18 selected interviewees to collect in-depth data and triangulate the questionnaire and English proficiency test results. The results indicated that, although the participants' needs in English language skills did not differ significantly, it is imperative to prioritize them in ESP courses to meet bankers' language needs in the bank's international departments. It is also recommended that ESP teachers employ a range of pedagogical and teaching strategies to assist learners in overcoming their barriers to communication.

Keywords: Bank Melli Iran; Course Design; English for Specific Purposes; International Banking; Situation Needs Analysis

1. Introduction

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a branch of applied linguistics (Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Tahririan & Chalak, 2019) that aims to teach

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learners how to use English effectively in academic or professional environments. When designing ESP courses, it is crucial for course designers to consider the specific needs of the learners in particular contexts. It has been highlighted by many classic needs analysis specialists, including Basturkmen (2010), Brown (1995), Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998), and Hutchinson and Waters (1987). According to Basturkmen, conducting a needs analysis can facilitate the development of efficacious ESP courses and programs. Many modern ESP specialists, such as Fiorito (2019), Khalili and Tahririan (2023), Musdalifah et al. (2024), and Salmani Nodoushan (2020), claimed that a course lacking needs analysis is deficient in defining the specific and targeted objectives that are necessary for favorable results. They suggested that through needs analysis procedures, novel ESP curricula can be generated from diverse fields, and pre-existing courses can be appraised and modified to ensure that the language skills taught are pertinent to the contemporary requisites of the respective trades or occupations.

One of these trades or occupations is international banking, and like other countries, it is a crucial element of Iran's economy. Employing a thorough needs analysis protocol that accurately reflects the English language needs of banking students and professionals in the banking industry and delineates the specific subject matter that should be taught in academic institutions would benefit all of the stakeholders involved. The study presented herein can make a noteworthy contribution to improving Iran's international banking system. Specifically, it has emphasized the importance of utilizing a needs analysis approach as a foundational step toward constructing and enhancing ESP courses within the international banking system.

This study aimed to enhance the alignment between the bankers' English language proficiency in their professional setting and the English language training programs offered by the training departments of financial institutions.

2. Background

The financial and banking system of Iran is the subject of few thorough needs analysis studies, although other areas of study perform many such analyses. Mazdayasna and Tahririan (2008) investigated the ESP needs of nursing and midwifery students in Iran. The study aimed to examine the foreign language learning needs of Iranian undergraduate medical science students in nursing and midwifery faculties. Masoumpanah and Tahririan (2013) looked at hotel receptionists' target situation needs. It was an effort to conduct a target situation needs analysis and a systematic textbook review for tourism students. Nilfroush and Chalak (2019) investigated the English language needs of engineers in the Isfahan steel company. This research aimed to discover the English language skills required for engineers' effective job

performance. Based on the findings obtained from these studies, revising the current professional training programs seems necessary to offer an appropriate ESP course curriculum, and the studies showed that needs analysis and materials evaluation go hand in hand; needs analysis determines the needs of learners, and evaluation determines how well the program serves these needs.

The international banking system and its associated industries are among the professions that have expanded substantially in recent years, and various empirical and detailed research studies on the communication needs of bankers and financial professionals have been conducted around the world. Moseley (2016) performed an ESP needs analysis on bankers in Oman to see whether banking students are gaining the necessary language skills in the professional context of Oman's Colleges of Applied Sciences. Afzal et al. (2020) examined the English writing needs and patterns among bank managers at Pakistan's Askari Bank Limited. By examining various factors, including the needs, wants, and lacks that contribute to their actual learning experiences, Al Khulaifi and Khalil (2021) conducted a needs analysis to define the communication needs of banking students in Kuwait. Indonesian Islamic Banking students' need for online English for Academic Purposes (EAP) was the subject of another research by Yunita (2022). An exploratory research conducted by Jeannette (2022) examined how English was used by Benin's banking, tourism, and travel personnel. Highlighting their needs, wants, lacks, and attitudes toward English was an effort to investigate the communication needs of these employees in their jobs. The findings of these studies revealed that the learners had significant challenges with different language skills. The results also indicated that the employees' opinions regarding English significantly impact how they perceive their needs, desires, and shortages. The finding provided valuable information for creating a curriculum or ESP course that would fulfill the communication demands of the staff and assure their effectiveness at work. Regarding online learning, it seems that learners prefer online learning platforms, whether a virtual tool to substitute for in-person instruction or the learning management system (LMS). The crucial variables affecting students' learning in online contexts are (1) the effective length of virtual sessions, (2) the language utilized, and (3) the learning activities.

However, there has been relatively little research on the topic of needs analysis and ESP in the Iranian banking and financial contexts, which is the subject of this study. Mohammadzadeh et al. (2015) analyzed the English language requirements of the Saderat Bank employees in Mashhad, Iran, to evaluate the degree to which staff must use English now and in the future and identify their difficulties. Alaei (2019) conducted a needs analysis study to examine the linguistic requirements of Iranian bank clerks working in international departments or foreign currency operations and their related sub-

departments based on their wants, needs, and requirements. Amerian and Marefat (2019) conducted another study to understand the specific English language needs of Iranian BA students studying Business and Economics and employers' expectations of them in the workplace. Takrousta et al. (2020) conducted a study to evaluate an English language textbook for banking purposes. The *English for Bankers* book was created by the English language specialists of the Export Development Bank of Iran (EDBI). It was developed as a response to a needs analysis study conducted by the bank's personnel and was expected to be assessed by language experts and staff members. Pirmoradian et al. (2023) investigated the English language needs of bank clerks in the banking system of Iran as target population by using the needs analysis model proposed by Hutchinson and Waters (1987) and its subordinate components known as (1) wants, (2) lacks, and (3) necessities.

Although bank employees had different wants, needs, and necessities, the results of the studies revealed that, while all four primary English skills were considered necessary for the profession, employers emphasized productive English skills significantly more. Furthermore, the researchers discovered a substantial discrepancy between the current English proficiency level of the staff and the expectations expressed by both the staff and managers themselves. Conducted studies also showed that a course lacking needs analysis is deficient in defining the specific objectives that are necessary for favorable results, and the current research has the potential to address gaps identified in previous studies, specifically concerning incorporating different stakeholder perspectives across diverse contexts, using a comprehensive needs analysis model and applying different instruments for collecting data. Its purpose was to investigate the English language needs of bankers and finance professionals at IBD of BMI, variations in their English language needs in different departments, and the English language skills that are required to study in training courses and critical considerations to provide empirical data to design ESP courses for them in the educational system of Iran. The following research questions have been addressed in this study to achieve the objectives mentioned above:

- What English language skills do bankers and finance professionals need to possess in the occupational context of IBD of Bank Melli Iran?
- How do the language needs of bankers and finance professionals vary at different departments of the IBD of Bank Melli Iran?
- What should the decision-makers consider when designing ESP courses for bankers and finance professionals in occupational contexts?

3. Method

The present study investigated the English language needs of bankers and finance professionals at the IBD of BMI to design an appropriate ESP course for them. It focused on the viewpoints of relevant parties within the occupational context of this research. Due to the lack of a thorough study on the English needs of bankers and finance professionals in the banking context of Iran, this topic was selected, and (1) a non-experimental design and (2) a quantitative descriptive methodology were adopted to adequately describe the situation of the intended population.

Questionnaires and proficiency tests are perhaps the best quantitative and descriptive methods for collecting respondents' perspectives (Babbie, 1990). The paradigm of pragmatism served as the foundation for the methodology of this study, and in establishing or developing a curriculum, needs analysis as a pragmatic activity plays a crucial role (Mohd Basari, 2018; Robinson, 1991).

Figure 1.

Needs Analysis Model of This Study (Adapted from Dudley-Evans & St. John, 1998)

This research also used the needs analysis model (Figure 1) proposed by Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998). It gave us a chance to thoroughly understand the participants' demands within the framework of learning and teaching ESP at the IBD of BMI. A few slight modifications were made to the original Dudley-Evans and St. John's needs analysis model to minimize misunderstanding and improve efficiency.

The study was completed between April 2022 and September 2022 in the occupational context of IBD of BMI. This financial institution comprises two essential departments, each employing a group of bank clerks: (a) the International Department and (b) the Foreign Guarantees Department. This binary structure enables each department to extend services that accurately correspond to the distinctive requirements of its market. The fact that one of the researchers is a bank manager at BMI made it easier for him to go through the administrative processes and get the consent of the officials to run the study. In addition, the availability of a sufficient number of bankers, finance professionals, and bank managers to participate in the study and the required number of facilities made it possible for him to select the IBD of BMI as the context of the study to contextualize the main issues addressed in this study and to make the study as authentic as possible.

3.1. Participants

The participants of the study were bankers and finance professionals from the IBD of BMI. Convenience sampling methods were used to choose them. These methods were selected because they provided an easy way to permit involvement in the study while also enabling the most suitable fit, collecting the most significant amount of possible information, and the ability to acquire a more profound knowledge of the situation. This sampling methodology corresponds with the pragmatic paradigm of the study since it is used throughout the investigation and gives the optimal possible solution to the research questions. Of the 130 bankers, finance professionals, and bank managers of the IBD of BMI as the whole sample, 90 participants took the proficiency test, and 88 returned the questionnaire. They were both males and females, and their ages ranged from 38 to 52. They had an average of 20 years of working experience in the different departments of that financial institution. Interviews were conducted with 18 interviewees to collect adequate in-depth data and triangulate the questionnaire and English proficiency test results. To increase the opportunity for the interview, this group of 18 interviewees comprised six bankers, six finance professionals, and six bank managers who were available for the study.

3.2. Instruments

Different instruments were used in this study to obtain information on participants. The first one is the *English Test for International Communication (TOEIC)*. It is a skill-based English proficiency test for non-native speakers of English. The old version of the *TOEIC* is more common, and it is more advantageous for intermediate to advanced-level language learners, so it was applied in this study to gain an understanding of the differences between the

bankers' target situations or needs and their present situations, which are connected to the English language information about the learners, and the learners' shortages. They are two essential elements of this study's needs analysis model. The results of this test were employed to arrive at a complete picture of the perceptions of the bankers' needs for the various English language skills at the IBD of BMI.

A bilingual *English Language Needs Questionnaire* was also used in this study to address the research questions and make sure bankers understand their language needs. According to the proficiency test results and Dudley-Evans and St. John's (1998) needs analysis model factors, a valid and reliable seven-point Likert-scale-based questionnaire was developed. These factors included (a) learners' professional information, (b) personal information, (c) English language information, (d) learners' lacks, and (e) their needs from the course. The bilingual questionnaire is especially helpful for topics that include vocabulary that may need to be better recognized in one of the languages since it gives respondents an easy way to assess their understanding quickly. It was used to address research questions and to explore the variations in the bankers' opinions of their needs.

A pilot study was conducted with 15 male and female experts selected randomly from a larger group of bankers and finance professionals to check the reliability and validity of the questionnaire. The face and content validity of the questionnaire were also checked prior to conducting the study. The questionnaire was evaluated by the supervisor, advisor, and ESP experts in banking, including ESP teachers and researchers, regarding the language, structure, jargon, aims, and rationales behind the questionnaire. Their concerns and pinpointed issues were reflected in designing the final edition of the questionnaire, and they authenticated the questionnaire in English as the appropriate instrument to assess participants' needs.

Based on the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) table proposed by Lawshe (1975), with 15 experts, the minimum CVR critical value for each item is 0.49. CVR was evaluated for all of the items in the questionnaire, and the acceptable Content Validity Index (CVI) equals 0.79, and items with a CVI lower than that were removed. Then, the Cronbach Alpha level was used to estimate the scale's reliability. The reason was to ensure the questions were consistent in assessing desired variables. The Cronbach's alpha values were more than 0.70 for the English Language Needs Questionnaire, which indicated moderately high reliability, internal consistency, and homogeneity. However, other crucial aspects besides validity and reliability should be considered when designing a questionnaire. These included the questionnaire length, the order of the questions, the language and wording, and recall bias. Regarding all of these

criteria, some questionnaire items were omitted, and some were modified by the researchers.

In many research studies, questionnaires and interviews go hand in hand to provide the opportunity to ask for more detailed information and have a deeper understanding of the participants' attitudes and beliefs, and this study was no exception. Therefore, the interview questions were developed to collect comprehensive data about bankers' language expectations and needs; accordingly, to get informative and in-depth reports of the participants' perspectives on the English language skills needs for the ESP program, interviews with a group of research participants were conducted. It gave the researchers a complete picture of the problem at hand. One strategy for checking the validity of the interview is to create a pattern of questions that enables internal consistency checking. Additionally, as the validity of an interview relies on the interviewer's skill and the replies of the participants, four essential procedures were employed to gather valid data via interviews: getting ready for the interview, arranging the interview, making sure that the meaningful interaction is available, and after the interview organizing the collected data (Richards, 2009). Triangulating the interview with other sorts of data collection procedures, such as the questionnaire and the English proficiency test, was another technique to improve the validity of the interview. In addition, validity was assured by having supervisors and coworkers review the interview questions. A timetable for each interview reminded the researchers how to perform the interviews, and it improved the interview's reliability.

In order to eliminate interviewees' ambiguity and misunderstanding, to get detailed information, and to minimize their stress, the researchers conducted interviews in Persian. However, there may be issues with syntax and semantics when translating from one language to another. Bracken and Barona (1991) suggested using back-translation by properly educated individuals in both languages to address these issues. The researchers transcribed and translated the interview questions into Persian since they are proficient enough in two languages and have knowledge about the research. The interview was kept brief and to the point and was so arranged that the interviewees remained interested throughout the interview. A semi-structured interview guide was developed. It consisted of different themes (personal information, professional information in the occupational contexts, language information about learners, their expressed need and necessity for the ESP programs, and environmental situations) and about 24 questions that directed the conversation toward the research topic during the interview (cf. Cridland et al., 2015). The interview format was flexible, which allowed the opportunity to change the order of the questions (cf. Turner & Hagstrom-Schmidt, 2022).

3.3. Procedure

In this research, descriptive statistical analysis was employed to clarify the response structure of the participants to the questionnaire (cf. Nitko & Brookhart, 2007); the coded replies of the participants were analyzed to identify their responses for each of the questionnaire items and to describe the results clearly. Mean values and standard deviations were used to show participants' average perceptions of their English language needs. The independent samples *t*-test procedure was also employed to compare the responses' mean values and see whether there were any statistically significant variations in the participants' judgments of their needs in English language skills.

The interviews were analyzed using a descriptive approach. All transcripts of the audio-taped interview data had to be checked and signed by the interviewees to ensure the researcher received and recorded data appropriately. Following that, themes, phrases, and words were used to code the data in this study. This classification reduced the data to a reasonable size and enabled the discovery of new groups and themes. The researchers coded the themes, phrases, and words associated with the elements of the study's needs analysis model.

In the present study, the researchers had a dual emic role. They played a significant role in different steps of conducting the research as consultants, collaborators, moderators, and researchers to understand the language needs of the participants. The researchers tried to conduct and present the results honestly, correctly, and responsibly. Confidentiality and anonymity are essential concepts that were taken into consideration to secure the participants' identities (cf. Babbie, 2014), and it was the researchers' duty to maintain the participants' confidentiality.

4. Results

This part is structured into three distinct sections: The initial section presents the results of the *TOEIC*, followed by the results of the English language needs questionnaire in the subsequent section, and the third section outlines the findings of semi-structured interviews.

At first, the two groups of participants (45 participants from the International Department and 45 participants from the Foreign Guarantees Department) were invited to take an English proficiency test to determine their current knowledge of the language. The results showed that none of the participants attained a score higher than 100 or half of the maximum possible score of 200. It indicated that they are at the intermediate level of English language proficiency.

Table 1
Independent Samples t-Test for the Total Score of TOEIC

Groups	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Group (a)	45	61.81	9.48	-2.29	83.43	0.02
Group (b)	45	67.06	12.03			

The t-test results showed that the mean scores of the participants in groups (a) and (b) significantly differed ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$), and the participants in group (b) obtained a marginally higher mean score for the total score (Table 1). So, it can be inferred that the participants in that group exhibit a higher degree of English language proficiency.

In the second section, the results of language needs questionnaire were reported. They were reported in the form of mean values and *t*-tests. The language needs questionnaire consisted of 68 question items. It was categorized into three distinct sections: the background information of the participants, the findings on the participants' needs concerning their general English language proficiency, and the findings on the participants' needs concerning English language tasks and sub-skills.

The participants' background information comprised three distinct sections. It provided general information on the participants, their English language proficiency levels, and the importance of English language use in occupational settings. Out of the total number of participants, which was 88 who took the questionnaire, the majority, comprising 77 (87.5%) individuals, were male, while the remaining 11(12.5%) individuals were female. Most of them self-assessed their proficiency in English language skills, ranging from grades D to C+. This indicates that most of them were at an intermediate English language proficiency level. The study's results also revealed the participants' perspectives on the importance of ESP in occupational contexts. Specifically, 55.5% of participants considered the ESP programs most important, while 35.4% deemed it important. A smaller 5.8% proportion of participants regarded it as moderately important, and only 3.3% perceived it as having little importance. Notably, none of the participants considered the ESP programs to be unimportant.

The second part of the Needs Questionnaire included questions that required the participants to evaluate their needs for general language skills to perform their duties in professional contexts, ranging from (1) most needed to (6) not needed at all. Table 2 displays the participants' needs for English language skills.

Table 2
Independent Samples T-Test for the Participants' Needs for English Language Skills

Language Skills	Group (a)		Group (b)		<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Listening	2.03	1.20	2.25	1.29	-0.82	0.40
Speaking	1.85	1.28	2.11	1.28	-0.95	0.34
Reading	2.07	1.31	2.09	1.08	-0.07	0.93
Writing	2.13	1.29	2.16	1.20	-0.11	0.91
Vocabulary	1.96	1.22	2.18	1.26	-0.83	0.40
Grammar	2.34	1.30	2.46	1.19	-0.45	0.65

Mean values show that most participants reported a significant need for general language skills. Furthermore, the results of group (a) demonstrated a marginally distinct trend compared to group (b). Most participants in group (a) showed a higher need for speaking ($M = 1.85$). Vocabulary and listening were at the next levels. In group (b), reading was deemed most necessary, with a mean value of 2.09, and speaking and writing were also considered necessary. The participants in both groups indicated that grammar was the least essential skill. The *t*-test indicated no statistically significant differences between the mean values of group (a) and group (b).

The third part of the questionnaire was designed to investigate the participants' needs for various tasks and sub-skills of the English language. The results are organized based on the answers provided by the participants in each group to the questions about seven language sub-skills. The mean values are utilized to present the data as they exhibited distinct patterns regarding the degree of English language task requirements by the participants. The *t*-test results indicated variations in their needs for English language tasks and activities.

Table 3 (below) shows the participants' needs for various tasks and sub-skills of the English language. It ranged from the most needed (1) to not need (6). Regarding listening skills, most participants in group (a) expressed a desire to improve their ability to listen to customers, as indicated by a mean score of 1.90. Following this, the participants also identified receiving spoken instructions/advice and listening to presentations and discussions in international meetings as areas where they would benefit from further practice. The participants in group (b) assigned the highest priority to listening to customers, with a mean score of 2.13. It was followed by receiving spoken instructions/advice and listening to presentations and discussions in international meetings.

Table 3
Independent Samples t-test for the Participants' Need for Language Tasks

Tasks	Group A		Group B		<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Listening						
1. Receiving spoken instructions/advice	1.96	1.16	2.14	0.81	-0.84	0.40
2. Listening to presentations and discussions in international meetings	2.10	1.11	2.42	1.09	-1.36	0.17
3. Listening to customers	1.90	0.95	2.13	1.04	-1.08	0.28
4. Listening to colleagues	2.47	1.17	2.54	0.95	-0.30	0.75
5. Listening to the radio or television programs and other English media	2.24	1.23	2.69	1.24	-1.70	0.09
Speaking						
6. Talking to a variety of audiences	2.11	1.13	2.43	1.19	-1.29	0.19
7. Asking and answering questions during the group or team	2.39	0.97	2.59	1.10	-0.90	0.36
8. Introducing yourself and others in a variety of situations	1.99	1.09	2.41	1.12	-1.78	0.07
9. Giving a presentation	1.91	1.17	2.12	1.21	-0.82	0.41
10. Stating opinions or ideas about different topics	2.25	1.15	2.61	1.10	-1.50	0.13
11. Speaking to foreigners	2.16	1.20	2.16	1.16	0.00	1.00
12. Making requests	2.32	1.11	2.39	1.00	-0.31	0.75
13. Talking over the phone	2.53	1.27	2.79	1.35	-0.93	0.35
14. Pronunciation	1.87	1.10	2.14	0.94	-1.23	0.21
Reading						
15. Reading reports	2.12	1.20	2.24	1.14	-0.48	0.63
16. Checking documents	2.05	1.11	2.17	1.07	-0.51	0.60
17. Reading textbooks	1.86	1.13	2.03	1.12	-0.70	0.48
18. Reading academic journals	2.12	1.00	2.49	1.23	-1.54	0.12
19. Reading instructions or product and process descriptions	2.03	1.01	2.40	1.21	-1.55	0.12
20. Searching the Internet English resources	2.14	1.07	2.38	1.13	-1.02	0.30
21. Reading office documents, e.g. business letters	2.10	1.02	2.68	1.24	-2.39	0.01
22. Reading workplace signs, rules, and notices	2.05	1.05	2.54	1.15	-2.08	0.03

Tasks	Group A		Group B		<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Writing						
23. Writing reports	2.05	1.12	2.30	1.03	-1.08	0.27
24. Writing research papers, articles, and reviews for scientific journals	2.17	1.19	2.28	1.20	-0.43	0.66
25. Writing job applications	2.12	1.14	2.40	1.19	-1.12	0.26
26. Writing product descriptions	2.00	0.91	2.38	1.17	-1.70	0.09
27. Writing emails	2.28	1.11	2.97	1.41	-2.55	0.01
28. Writing business letters	2.35	1.24	2.96	1.38	-1.96	0.05
29. Taking notes	2.40	1.22	2.77	1.14	-1.46	0.14
30. Writing a resume	2.28	1.33	2.42	1.17	-0.52	0.60
31. Filling out forms	2.17	1.23	2.28	0.96	-0.46	0.64
32. Describing diagrams, tables, and graphs	2.03	0.95	2.41	1.22	-1.63	0.10
33. Writing instructions	2.00	1.09	2.33	1.26	-1.31	0.19
Vocabulary						
34. General vocabulary	1.93	1.08	2.19	1.03	-1.15	0.25
35. Technical terms	1.80	1.00	1.72	0.98	0.37	0.70
Grammar						
36. Grammatical structure for general communications	2.05	1.09	2.27	1.01	-0.98	0.32
37. Grammar structures frequently used in scientific discourse	1.79	1.10	2.05	1.15	-1.08	0.28

Regarding speaking skills, based on the mean values observed in both groups, it can be inferred that most participants thought they required extensive practice across all speaking tasks and activities. The patterns of ratings exhibited by the participants in both groups are marginally distinct. In group (a), most participants expressed a need for improvement in pronunciation ($M = 1.87$) by giving presentations and introducing themselves and others in several situations, following closely behind in order of priority. In group (b), most participants were assigned the highest rating for giving a presentation ($M = 2.12$), followed by pronunciation and speaking to foreigners in descending order.

Regarding reading skills, the results indicated that the mean values for both groups suggest that most participants perceived a significant need for extensive engagement with all reading tasks. Most participants indicated that their highest priority task was reading textbooks in both groups, with mean

scores of 1.86 and 2.03, respectively. In group (a), a majority of participants expressed the necessity of possessing the ability to read instructions or product and process descriptions ($M = 2.03$) and to read workplace signs, rules, and notices and checking documents ($M = 2.05$). Group (b) was required to possess the ability to check documents ($M = 2.17$) and read reports ($M = 2.24$).

Regarding writing skills, the results indicated that the mean values for both groups revealed a predominant perception among participants that they required extensive practice with all writing tasks. Within group (a), the majority of participants assigned higher priority to writing product descriptions, writing instructions ($M = 2.00$), and describing diagrams, tables, and graphs ($M = 2.03$) in comparison to other writing tasks. Within group (b), the majority of participants assigned higher levels of importance to tasks such as writing research papers, articles, or reviews for scientific journals, filling out forms ($M = 2.28$), and writing reports ($M = 2.30$) in comparison to other writing tasks.

Concerning English language vocabulary tasks, the results presented here indicated that the mean values for both groups revealed a predominant perception that the most pressing need was for both types of vocabulary tasks, including general vocabulary and technical terms. They expressed a higher level of agreement with the importance and intensity of technical terms ($M = 1.80$ and 1.72).

Regarding grammar tasks and activities, the data presented indicated that the mean values for both groups demonstrated a prevalent perception among participants that they required extensive practice in both of the grammar tasks. The results also indicated that the two groups exhibited comparable response patterns, assigning greater importance to grammar structures frequently used in scientific discourse ($M = 1.79$ and 2.05).

The results obtained from the Questionnaire on English Language Needs indicated that participants were at the intermediate level of English language proficiency. Additionally, most of them said that speaking was the most needed ability, followed by listening, reading, and vocabulary. Grammar and writing, on the other hand, were seen to be less important. The t -test results indicated no statistically significant variations between the participants in the mentioned language tasks and activities. Nonetheless, notable variations were observed in the average scores for reading office documents, reading workplace signs, rules, and notices, composing emails, and drafting business letters ($p < 0.05$).

The final section presents the study's findings, which are based on the responses of 18 interviewees to the interview questions designed under this study needs analysis model. The interview questions were designed to elicit

data on all the components of this study's needs analysis model. Thematic analysis was used for data analysis in the interview section. Themes were extracted from the interview guide and assessed in light of the study's objectives. The findings were categorized based on shared factors and subsequently presented under the five primary factors outlined in the model: personal information, professional information, and language information of interviewees, their expressed need, and necessity for the ESP programs, and the viewpoints of the interviewees regarding environmental situations.

The personal information of the interviewees was delineated with the interviewees' inclinations and perspectives toward the ESP programs, their experiences in English language learning, their working experiences, and their educational and occupational backgrounds. They expressed their intention to enhance their English proficiency before commencing work or during their leisure time. They exhibited a vested interest in, and a favorable disposition towards, engaging in ESP programs, albeit some demonstrated a pessimistic outlook. The major factors contributing to their unfavorable disposition encompassed their study patterns, the ESP program content, and the instructional methodology and demeanor of the ESP instructors.

The second theme concerns professional information in occupational contexts. The findings of this part were related to English language activities in the banking industry. Authentic language was used in occupational contexts, while apparently, it was absent in the ESP courses. Proficiency in English vocabulary, including technical terminology and speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills, is crucial for success in the banking industry. The frequency with which these skills are utilized varies depending on the specific job and department. More evidence was discovered indicating a greater utilization of English language proficiency among bankers in the international department than those in the foreign guarantee department.

Regarding interviewees' language information, the findings revealed that they experienced challenges in all English language skills. The bankers believed that their highest proficiency was in reading skills. All interviewees employed various learning strategies to enhance their language skills, with cognitive, social, and metacognitive strategies being the most frequently utilized. They were tailored to align with the learners' preferred learning modes as opposed to their respective levels of language proficiency. The interviewees expressed difficulty with all of the language skills pertinent to the workplace, which necessitates the consideration of such issues by ESP instructors.

The fourth section is concerned with the interviewees' needs for the ESP programs. The need for English language skills in professional contexts can be the target need and serve as the ESP programs' focal point. Most bankers have expressed the necessity of possessing all language skills by implementing ESP

programs for their career-oriented objectives. The interviews found that while all bankers acknowledged the importance of vocabulary, most of them prioritized speaking as their most essential skill. Other required language skills included reading, writing, listening, and grammar.

As the fifth theme, the environmental context in which the ESP programs were implemented by the training departments of BMI was illustrated by relevant stakeholders. The consensus among the interviewees was that the training departments of banks did not offer adequate support for ESP teaching and learning. This implies that it would benefit banks to enhance the prominence of the ESP programs among bank clerks.

5. Discussion

Nearly all ESP courses deal with making learners capable of using English in their academic and occupational contexts (Donadio, 2019; Francomacaro, 2019; Naddeo, 2019; Pennarola, 2019). Due to the direct relation of academic courses to specific workers and clerks in particular fields, they must be adjusted clearly to their specific needs and requirements. Such coordination is achieved through a thoughtful and attentive needs analysis. In this study, the English language needs of bankers and finance professionals working at the IBD of BMI were investigated through implementing the *TOEIC*, the Questionnaire on English Language Needs, and Semi-Structured Interviews. Three research questions were developed to achieve the objectives of the study. The first research question pertained to the English language needs of the participants in their occupational context. The second research question provided significant information related to the variations in the English language proficiency needs of the participants in two departments of the IBD of BMI. The last research question concerned with developing materials and designing ESP courses for bank clerks in the banking system of Iran.

Being the primary consideration of the first research question, the English language needs of the participants were found to be associated with elements (a), (b), and (h) of the needs analysis model that focused on learners' professional and personal information and also environmental situations of learning context. In accordance with the participants' perceptions within occupational contexts, the most essential skills were speaking, reading, and vocabulary use. Grammar and writing, on the other hand, were seen as less important. The study found that the participants' requirements were primarily linked to their needs and specific English activities and tasks in the target situations.

As observed in this study, the significance of speaking activities and tasks within the occupational context aligns with the findings of analogous studies in other workplace settings in Iran. Specifically, speaking tasks in a face-to-face

manner are widely regarded as the most frequently demanded and essential activities for successful performance. The integration of multiple domains of the English language, which is one of the results of this study, is corroborated by other contemporary studies on ESP. According to Nilforoush and Chalak (2019), engineering students must have access to engineering-specific and general content for daily communication in English. The results of this study raised doubts regarding the categorization and differentiation of English language needs in ESP occupational contexts and those in academic contexts. In summary, bankers must possess integrated English language skills in occupational contexts. The research also revealed that the specific needs of the participants were associated with environmental situations, encompassing learner attributes, classroom culture, ESP instructors, and the efficacy of ESP programs.

The second research question provided significant results related to the variations in the English language proficiency needs of the participants in various departments of the IBD of Bank Melli Iran. The study identified three distinct patterns in the participants' needs: no change, an increase, and a decrease in their needs. According to bank managers, these variations in participants' needs depended on various factors, including the exigencies of the intended contexts, the learners' awareness of their educational objectives, and the environmental situations. Bankers and finance professionals' different responsibilities in the two departments of the IBD of BMI and their perceptions regarding their acquired knowledge may also result in variations in their English language needs, as proposed by ESP scholars such as Lowe (2009) and Robinson (1991). Familiarity with these variations is crucial to designing ESP programs, and it may facilitate designing ESP courses that align with the learners' needs.

Concerning the third research question and for developing materials and designing ESP courses, this study revealed that, although English is not the primary mode of oral communication in their professional environment, bank clerks preferred training programs that facilitate their adaptation to workplace demands. It is recommended that these courses maintain an equitable emphasis on communication strategies and cross-cultural understanding. In addition, the curriculum of an ESP course must be developed in a way that meets the needs of learners by providing them with relevant language experiences. It can be achieved by prioritizing tasks and activities that facilitate learning. Moreover, the proposed ESP programs should emphasize developing all language skills to facilitate effective communication in genuine contexts.

6. Conclusion

Like other studies conducted in the field of ESP, such as those by Di Martino and Polese (2019), Grego, (2019), Hyun Hyo (2013), and Toluei and Tahririan

(2023), the research findings indicated that ESP programs should equip learners effectively with the necessary skills to use English proficiently in professional contexts. It is also recommended that ESP instructors should give learners special attention, improve their familiarity with specific texts and tasks (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007), and motivate them to use a wide variety of language activities and tasks to improve their language abilities.

As a result, the researchers developed a new needs analysis model (Figure 2). It encompassed all the primary factors and essential features of the Dudley-Evans and St. John's (1998) model in a new format. The revised model includes all variables about the learners, thereby highlighting the crucial interdependence between the learners and other components of the needs analysis model. It introduces novel viewpoints to develop research conducted previously by essential figures in this area, such as Basturkmen (2010), Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998), and Hutchinson and Waters (1987).

Figure 2.

Redesigned Needs Analysis Model

The new model has three primary factors encompassing all the factors involved in an ESP needs analysis. The learner factors are placed at the center of the new needs analysis model, with a particular emphasis on four key areas: their background knowledge and abilities in English, their attitudes and areas of interest, their preferred learning styles and strategies, and their demands from the ESP courses. The professional information as the second factor, focused on the participants' perceptions in various occupational settings regarding their approach to language use by learners in real-life situations. The redesigned model incorporates another significant factor pertaining to the

teaching and learning environment, encompassing three key aspects: institutional factors, the opportunity to practice the English language and classroom interaction. In summary, the redesigned needs analysis model can provide insight into individuals' needs in professional and academic contexts and may uncover disparities between the perspectives on needs held by diverse participants in these two contexts. However, it proves to be more efficient regarding time consumption, simpler to analyze data, and easier to interpret.

After conducting a needs analysis study and presenting the redesigned needs analysis model, a content-based ESP Course was designed to fulfill the needs of learners in the future workplace context. It comprised various main topics, subtopics, functions, and specific vocabularies. A task would be given during the proposed ESP course, and all language skills would be practiced while understanding content, discussing problems, and completing exercises. One task for reading would be given to every class; vocabulary would be learned. The proposed course aims to improve the learners' language abilities in all areas.

Table 4

Essential Variables for the Proposed ESP Course

Variables	Considered Factors
Course duration	Extensive (can be changed to intensive duration according to the need and interest of participants)
Participants	Bankers and finance professionals
Group size	Medium group (can be changed according to the availability of resources)
Location	The training department of BMI
Mode of learning	Class-teaching
Trainers	ESP Practitioners
Evaluation	Summative evaluation

Table 4 demonstrates the designed ESP course for bankers and finance professionals in IBD of BMI. It will be of 36 credit hours. The sessions will be held one day a week, on Monday. Each session will be of 1.5 hours. The proposed timing for sessions will be 07:00 am to 02:30 pm. The course is designed for experienced bank clerks in IBD of BMI. It is designed according to the needs of participants. It will lead to using an 'eclectic' approach to teaching where the ESP practitioner can switch between different methods to teach how to use language professionally in a business setting. Worksheets will be used to have certain practices by assigning different tasks. Summative assessments will be carried out, and at the end of the program, participants are supposed to

be proficient enough in language skills. They will be able to communicate effectively in English and use language skills to perform their duties better in occupational contexts.

The results of this study have practical implications for policymakers, materials developers, syllabus designers, and professionals in different fields of English language teaching, particularly those involved in developing courses for bank clerks in the banking system of Iran. On the other hand, the outcomes are advantageous for both instructors and students of ESP. ESP Educators in the field of banking may concentrate on the needs of the bankers and finance professionals, specifically the areas that are commonly encountered by these professionals. In addition, they must address macro issues in ESP-related topics like the unequal distribution of power dynamics within the classroom and the pertinence of subject matter for students specializing in the banking field. It is also imperative for instructors of ESP to acknowledge the potential benefits of investing in their ESP learners and providing them with resources that enhance their linguistic and professional proficiencies (cf. Darvin & Norton, 2017). Furthermore, Scholars in the field of ESP in general, and EFL in the context of Iran in particular, may derive advantages from the findings of this investigation. It is suggested that ESP researchers may wish to broaden the scope of this investigation by conducting a more comprehensive ethnographic study, as proposed by Madison (2011), to gain a better comprehension of the requirements of banking and finance experts within the banking section of Iran.

All in all, before implementing a language curriculum, it is advisable for designers, educators, and instructors, mainly those responsible for developing English language programs, to conduct a thorough needs analysis. Completing this phase is imperative to create a course of superior quality that effectively caters to the authentic needs of the learners. As a result, a needs analysis should be done at the start of any course development, and it should ultimately lead to course evaluation. Course evaluation must be conducted once the needs analysis has established the course goals.

Authors' Statement

The authors discussed, conceived, and wrote the article together.

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